

Germanium Thermophotovoltaic Devices Achieving 7.3% Efficiency Under High-Temperature Emission by Empirical Calorimetry

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Abstract — We report the first empirical efficiency measurement of germanium-based thermophotovoltaic devices under high-temperature, high-irradiance conditions using a high view-factor calorimetric setup. Two TPV cell architectures were fabricated on p-type, highly doped (10^{17} cm^{-3}) Ge substrates, differing only in rear contact configuration. A standard device with a gold rear contact achieves a peak efficiency of 7.3 % and a power density of 1.77 W cm^{-2} at an emitter temperature of 1480 °C, while a PERC-type device reaches 6.3 % efficiency and 1.22 W cm^{-2} at 1426 °C. The superior performance of the standard device is attributed to lower series resistance, whereas the PERC design exhibits slightly higher efficiency at lower emitter temperatures (4.0 % vs. 3.8 % at 1150 °C) due to enhanced rear-surface reflectivity. A detailed TPV model has been developed and validated across both device architectures. The model identifies out-of-band optical losses as the dominant efficiency-limiting mechanism, primarily caused by strong free-carrier absorption in the highly doped Ge substrate. Using this model, we predict device performance under idealized spectral conditions commonly assumed in prior literature. For a simulated AlN/W spectrally selective emitter, efficiencies as high as 22.3 % at 1800 °C are obtained, consistent with previous semi-empirical predictions. In contrast, when previously reported Ge devices are modeled under the realistic graphite emitter spectrum used here, projected efficiencies decrease to as low as 8.1 % at 1480 °C. These results show that earlier projections remain valid but idealized and underscore the importance of emitter spectral engineering and substrate optimization. Finally, we present the first direct comparison of Ge and InGaAs TPV devices under identical conditions, demonstrating the superior performance of InGaAs while confirming the cost-driven competitiveness of Ge.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermophotovoltaic (TPV) devices convert thermal radiation, primarily in the infrared spectrum, emitted by a high-temperature source into electricity via the photovoltaic effect [1], [2]. This principle makes TPV systems particularly attractive for applications such as industrial waste heat recovery and thermal energy storage [3], [4], especially in the context of renewable energy integration. As renewable energy capacity continues to grow, the need for efficient, dispatchable storage solutions becomes increasingly critical. TPV-based thermal batteries [5], [6] offer a compelling approach for storing excess renewable energy in thermal form and delivering electricity on demand, particularly during periods when generation and consumption are misaligned.

A key distinction between TPV and conventional solar photovoltaic systems lies in the proximity of the device to the heat source [1], [2]. This close coupling benefits from the integration of a reflective mirror placed beneath the cell. This strategy allows unabsorbed radiation to be redirected back to the emitter, enhancing overall system efficiency through radiative recycling. Using this approach, TPV cells based on III-V semiconductor materials have demonstrated efficiencies above 40% [7], [8]. These materials are often

employed in advanced structures, such as “air-bridge” cells, which enhance back mirror reflectivity by exploiting the large refractive index contrast between air and metals like gold [7], [9]. However, the use of III-V materials entails high material and processing costs, limiting their industrial scalability [4].

Germanium (Ge) has historically been considered a cost-effective alternative for the fabrication of TPV devices. It has been widely used in the space industry as the bottom cell in multijunction solar cells, benefiting from mature processing techniques and good lattice matching with III-V materials. However, Ge presents specific challenges for TPV applications. For instance, its native oxide does not provide effective surface passivation, and its indirect bandgap inherently limits the open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}).

One of the most critical trade-offs in Ge-based TPV design lies in the doping concentration of the substrate. Higher doping levels improve the electrical performance by increasing V_{oc} and lowering the series resistance of the bulk, thus maximizing carrier collection [10], [11]. Nonetheless, elevated doping also increases free-carrier absorption (FCA), particularly for photon energies lower than the bandgap of the absorber, i.e. out-of-band (OOB) photons. These optical losses not only reduce TPV efficiency but also contribute to thermal management issues, as low energy absorbed photons by free carriers are transformed into heat rather than being reflected to the emitter.

Conversely, reducing the doping concentration enhances infrared transparency, allowing a larger fraction of OOB photons to reach the back mirror and be reflected back to the emitter. This boosts optical efficiency but degrades V_{oc} [12]. In addition, the longer diffusion lengths associated with lower doping levels make effective surface passivation increasingly critical. To address this, various strategies have been explored to create passivated contacts at the rear surface of the cells, including the implementation of back-surface field (BSF) structures [12], and the use of passivating dielectric stacks (e.g., $Al_2O_3/a-Si$) [13], [14], [15] for the development of passivated emitter and rear cell (PERC) architectures through the Laser Firing Contact technique (LFC) [13], [16], [17].

These design choices are reflected in the different structures reported in the literature for Ge TPV devices, which span a range of doping concentrations, contact schemes (with their associated active areas and shadowing factors, SF), and rear-side reflectors which deserves a thorough review. A summary of the reported efficiencies of Ge-based TPV devices, along with the main methodological assumptions used for their calculation, is provided in Table 1.

Previous efficiency reports for Ge-based TPV cells are limited and rely exclusively on semi-empirical methods to estimate conversion efficiency under idealized assumptions (see Table 1). In 1963, Wedlock et al. [18] reported a 4.2 % conversion efficiency for a Ge p-i-n device illuminated by a wolfram lamp at 2400 K through a long-pass filter (cutoff at 1 μm), under an incident power density of 282 $mW \cdot cm^{-2}$. This calculation followed a solar-cell-like approach, neglecting sub-bandgap absorption and radiative exchange, unlike modern TPV efficiency definitions. More recently, Fernández et al. [13], [19] reported a 16.5 % efficiency for a LFC-PERC type Ge TPV cell. However, the efficiency calculation assumed a cut-off spectrum using a 1100 °C microstructured wolfram emitter, effectively neglecting the absorption of OOB photons. Van der Heide et al. [14], [20] do not report TPV efficiencies, but their work provides relevant insights into PERC-type devices with LFC. They investigated the effect of reducing the bulk doping concentration from $1 \times 10^{17} cm^{-3}$ to $1 \times 10^{15} cm^{-3}$ and examined the impact of a selective Er_2O_3 emitter on

short-circuit current and overall device reflectivity under the AM1.5G spectrum for both 1 sun and 20 suns. More recently, Martín et al. [12] reported efficiencies for BSF-type Ge TPV cells fabricated on low ($\sim 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), medium ($\sim 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), and high ($\sim 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) doped substrates, with the highest efficiency (23.2%) obtained for the highest doped case. However, this estimate is also based on a theoretical AlN-coated W spectrally selective emitter that suppressed OOB radiation. In a different approach, Gamel et al. [21] investigated a cost-effective alternative to epitaxial growth for the electron-selective contact, analyzing the use of phosphorus-doped nanocrystalline silicon for the n-type electrode instead of epitaxial layers, combined with an aluminum rear contact. Their model predicts TPV efficiencies of 6.5 % and 2.9 % for medium ($\sim 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) and low ($\sim 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) doping levels when irradiated with a blackbody emitter at 1328 °C and 1029 °C, respectively.

Thus, all prior efficiency values were not obtained through direct calorimetric measurements but were instead derived from models, in most of the cases incorporating idealized assumptions, primarily concerning the spectral distribution of incident radiation on the cell.

Table 1. Summary of the efficiency reports for Ge-based TPV cells

	TPV cell design					TPV efficiency calculation/measurement conditions				
	Substrate doping(s) (cm^{-3})	Front surface	Rear surface	Cell Active Area [cm^2]	SF [%]	Emitter	Emitter-cell optical cavity effect	Electric power	Heat dissipated	TPV Efficiency
Wedlock et al [18]	p-i-n No dopings reported	p-Ge	n-Ge	1.29	-	1500w Wolfram lamp	Not considered	Exp. (wolfram lamp)	Not considered	4.2 % at 2127 °C (Simulated)
Fernandez et al [13], [19]	10^{17} 10^{16} 10^{15}	ARC/GaAs/ GaInP	PERC (Si/SiO ₂ - Al LFC)	1.55	-	Sim. (micro-structured wolfram with spectral cut off)	Not considered	Exp. (under flash lamp)	Sim.	16.5 % 1100 °C (simulated)
Martin et al [12]	10^{17} 10^{16} 10^{15}	GaAs	Al-BSF	0.09	6	Sim. (AlN/W [22])	Not considered	Exp. (under high intensity laser)	Sim.	23.2 % (10^{17}) 1800 °C 21.5 % (10^{16}) 1800 °C 20.6 % (10^{15}) 1800 °C (simulated)
Gamel et al [21]	10^{16} 10^{15}	nc-Si(n)	Al	0.64	~ 13	Sim. (Blackbody spectra)	Not considered	Exp. (under flash lamp)	Sim	6.5 % (10^{16}) 1328 °C 2.9 % (10^{15}) 1029 °C (simulated)
This work (CONV)	10^{17}	GaAs/ GaInP	Au	0.85	19	Exp. (graphite)	Exp. (High view factor)	Exp. (under high temp emitter)	Exp. (calorimetry)	7.3 % 1480 °C (empirical)
This work (PERC)	10^{17}	GaAs/ GaInP	PERC (a-SiC(i)/Al ₂ O ₃ /a-SiC LFC - Cr/Au)	0.85	19	Exp. (graphite)	Exp. (High view factor)	Exp. (under high temp emitter)	Exp. (calorimetry)	6.3 % 1425 °C (empirical)

This work reports the first fully empirical determination of the efficiency of Ge-based TPV devices. To that end, we developed two types of Ge-based TPV cells: a conventional device (CONV) with a gold rear mirror directly deposited on the Ge substrate, and a PERC-type cell, building upon the concept proposed in [13]. Our design utilizes a highly doped (10^{17} cm^{-3}) Ge substrate and incorporates the rear-contact scheme introduced in our earlier work [15], which integrates a multilayer dielectric stack (a-SiCx:H(i)/Al₂O₃/a-SiC) for effective surface passivation and enhanced rear-side reflectivity, along with localized

laser-fired punctual contacts to achieve low contact resistivity and efficient carrier collection.

The devices were characterized using a high-view-factor calorimetric setup equipped with a high-temperature graphite emitter [23], enabling simultaneous, direct measurement of both the electrical power output and the heat dissipated by the cell. This method provides a fully empirical determination of TPV efficiency, in contrast to prior studies that relied on semi-empirical models and idealized assumptions about the spectral distribution of incident radiation.

To get further insight of device performance, we developed a model that accurately reproduces our experimental results. This model is subsequently used to identify and quantify the dominant sources of efficiency loss, most notably, those related to OOB photon absorption in the highly doped Ge substrate. We also applied the model to previously reported device architectures, enabling a direct comparison of device efficiencies and a consistent re-evaluation of their predicted performance under the same assumptions and boundary conditions used in this study.

This article is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the methodology, including TPV cell fabrication, experimental characterization, and numerical simulation. Section 3 presents and discusses the results, while Section 4 compares them with the state of the art for both Ge and InGaAs devices, including the first direct comparison of Ge and InGaAs TPV cells measured under identical experimental conditions.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 MANUFACTURING

In this study, we used 4-inch p-type crystalline Ge wafers, 170 μm thick, oriented along the (100) plane, with a doping concentration of $N_A \approx 2 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Using these substrates, both a baseline Ge TPV cell and a PERC device were fabricated. A front view of the fabricated devices is shown in Figure 1, together with sketches of their respective architectures and a microscope image of the PERC localized rear contacts. A step-by-step visual representation of the manufacturing process can be found in Supplementary information S1.

Figure 1 Structural and visual details of the Ge TPV devices analyzed in this work. A) Front view of the fabricated devices, where the front contact design is identical in both cases. B) and C) Schematic view of the layer configuration for the CONV and PERC respectively (not to scale). D) Microscope image of the localized rear contacts used in the PERC configuration.

All samples underwent epitaxial growth of n-type GaAs (150 nm)/GaInP (50 nm) layers at the Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems (ISE) using metal-organic vapor phase epitaxy (MOVPE). This process simultaneously formed a contact layer for the

device emitter, passivated the surface [19], and created the pn junction via phosphorus diffusion in the Ge substrate.

For the front contact, all devices underwent a conventional photolithography followed by thermal evaporation (Joule effect) to deposit an AuGe/Ni/Au metal stack with thicknesses of 85/25/150, nm respectively. This metal scheme is well-established for forming ohmic contacts on n-type GaAs [24], [25] and typically requires a post-deposition annealing step to achieve lower resistivity. However, in our devices, the GaAs contact layer was limited to a thickness of only 150 nm. As a result, annealing the AuGe alloy caused the formation of metal spikes that penetrated through the pn junction, ultimately leading to device short-circuiting. To prevent this, all samples in this work were fabricated without front contact annealing. Consequently, the devices exhibit higher series resistance than expected from fully optimized ohmic contacts. Following the metal evaporation, an additional gold layer was electroplated onto the front contact to increase its height to approximately 5 μm , reducing fingers electrical resistance. The electroplating process, however, proved to be inconsistent, leading to variations in gold resistivity and ultimately contributing to the higher series resistance observed in the PERC device, identified as the main factor behind its lower performance at higher emitter temperature. Before the mesa photolithography step, the GaAs contact layer was selectively removed using an NH_4OH (30 %): H_2O_2 (30 %): H_2O solution in a 2:1:10 ratio for 30 s. This step exposed the underlying GaInP while preserving all other layers. Afterward, mesa photolithography and wet etching were performed to electrically isolate the individual devices. The mesa etching consisted of two additional selective steps. First, the GaInP layer was etched using 37 % HCl for 2 s. Second, pn-junction isolation was completed using an H_3PO_4 (85 %): H_2O_2 (30 %): H_2O mixture in a 1:6:3 ratio for 15 min, reaching depths of up to 5 μm and ensuring electrical isolation between neighbouring devices. All etching steps were conducted at room temperature and did not damage any of the other layers exposed during the process.

For the rear side, all wafers were chemically etched to remove approximately 5 μm of Ge, a critical step to eliminate residual contamination from the previous epitaxial growth which would otherwise result in the formation of an unintended parasitic rear junction, adversely affecting the device behavior. This etch was performed using a solution of H_3PO_4 (85 %): H_2O_2 (30 %): H_2O (1:6:3) with the front surface protected by photoresist.

For the CONV device, rear metallization was performed by thermally evaporating a 200 nm thick gold layer. In contrast, the PERC devices employed a rear-side dielectric passivation stack designed to enhance both surface passivation and optical reflectivity [15]. This stack consisted of 2 nm of hydrogenated amorphous silicon carbide (a-SiC_x:H) deposited by plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) at 400 °C, followed by 50 nm of aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) deposited via atomic layer deposition (ALD), and an additional 45 nm of amorphous silicon carbide (a-SiC) deposited at 370 °C. The Al_2O_3 layer in the stack also serves as a source of aluminum dopants for the subsequent formation of localized LFCs, as described in [15]. Laser firing injects aluminum dopant into the substrate, forming a BSF of p⁺-Ge that provides low resistivity and highly selective point-like contacts. For this process, a Talon 355-6 Nd:YVO₄ laser emitting pulsed ultraviolet light at a wavelength of 355 nm was used. The laser was set to a frequency of 20 kHz, delivering pulses of 9 ns with an emitting power of 11 mW, resulting in a fluence of 0.9 J/cm². The laser spot pattern, determined through previous electrical analysis [15], was configured with a 60 μm pitch and two pulses per spot. Finally, the rear-side metallization was completed by depositing a 5 nm chromium adhesion layer followed by a 200 nm gold layer across the entire rear surface. This step interconnects all rear point-like contacts and simultaneously forms the back surface reflector (BSR).

The final device features an device area of 1.05 cm² (0.85 cm² excluding the busbars), defined by the mesa pattern. A 500 μm separation is left outside the mesa region between adjacent devices to serve as a dicing street and ensure safe wafer cutting.

2.2 CHARACTERIZATION

The fabricated cells underwent comprehensive opto-electronic characterization, including optical reflectance measurements over an extended spectral range using Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometry with integrating spheres, external quantum efficiency (EQE) analysis, and both dark and illuminated current–voltage (I – V) characterization. A multi-flash solar simulator I – V measurement system based on a Xe pulsed light, commonly used for concentrated PV (CPV) cell characterization, was employed to evaluate the device performance under high-irradiance conditions [26].

Remarkably, the best-performing cells were characterized using a dedicated high-view-factor calorimetric setup, featuring a high-temperature graphite emitter positioned in the range of 0.7 mm from the front surface of the TPV cell [23]. This extremely close spacing produced an emitter-to-cell view factor close to 0.95, effectively forming an optical cavity that governs the complex radiative exchange between the emitter and the cell [27]. The experimental setup, described in detail in [23], operates in vacuum and includes a tunable high-power continuous-wave diode laser (RFLA500D, 915 nm, up to 500 W) laser for contactless heating of the emitter, as well as a precision calorimeter for measuring the heat dissipated by the cell. To ensure accurate thermal measurements, the TPV cell and the electrical probes (used to measure the output electricity) are maintained at room temperature using two independent cooling systems. This guarantees that all heat generated in the cell is directed through the calorimeter, rather than being dissipated through the electrical contacts. During each measurement, the cell voltage is held at its maximum power point (MPP), allowing the system to reach steady-state conditions. Under these controlled conditions, the TPV conversion efficiency can be directly determined as a function of the measured output power (P_{el}) and dissipated heat (Q_{dis}) as:

$$\eta_{TPV} = \frac{P_{el}}{P_{abs}} = \frac{P_{el}}{P_{el} + Q_{dis}} \quad (1)$$

2.3 TPV MODEL

A theoretical model was developed to reproduce the performance of the fabricated TPV devices and to gain insight into the underlying loss mechanisms. The goal of this model is to calculate TPV efficiency, as expressed in equation (1), by calculating the following two magnitudes: the net power absorbed by the cell (P_{abs}) and the corresponding P_{el} .

Calculating P_{abs} involves the computation of the radiative exchange between the emitter and the cell. To that end, we adopt the same approach used in recent literature reporting semi-empirical TPV efficiency values [28] which assumes that both the emitter and the cell are specular surfaces and form an infinitely extended co-planar optical cavity, in which case the absorbed radiative power can be estimated by the following expression [29]:

$$P_{abs} = A_e F_{ec} \int_0^{\infty} \epsilon_{eff}(\lambda) \cdot P_{BB}(T_e, \lambda) \cdot d\lambda \quad (2)$$

where A_e is the emitter area (more precisely, the aperture area that defines the opening through which radiation is transmitted in the experimental setup), F_{ec} is the emitter-to-cell view factor, $P_{BB}(T_e, \lambda)$ is the Planck equation of thermal radiation, which in turn depends on the emitter temperature (T_e) and the photon wavelength (λ), and $\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}(\lambda) = \varepsilon_e \cdot \varepsilon_c / (\varepsilon_e + \varepsilon_c - \varepsilon_e \cdot \varepsilon_c)$ is the effective emissivity, which depends on the emitter and cell emissivity, ε_e and ε_c , respectively. Both ε_e and ε_c are experimentally obtained through global reflectivity measurements at room temperature (see Supplementary information S2).

On the other hand, P_{el} is calculated as the product of the current and voltage at the cell MPP. This can be expressed as:

$$P_{el} = I \cdot V|_{\text{MPP}} \quad (3)$$

I and V are obtained from the well-established single-diode model:

$$I = I_L - I_0 \left(\exp \left[\frac{q(V + IR_S)}{nk_B T_c} \right] - 1 \right) - \frac{V + IR_S}{R_{sh}} \quad (4)$$

In this equation, k_B is Boltzmann's constant, T_c is the cell temperature, the shunt resistance (R_{sh}) is extracted by fitting to dark I - V characteristics, i.e., under the condition $I_L = 0$ (See Supplementary information S4). The remaining parameters, ideality factor (n), reverse saturation current (I_0), and series resistance (R_S), are obtained by fitting the model to experimental I - V characteristics measured at room temperature under high irradiance conditions, corresponding to different values of photogenerated current (I_L) (see Supplementary information S5). The I_L , which depends on the T_e , is calculated using the following expression [30]:

$$I_L = \frac{qF_{ec}}{hc} * A_e \int_0^{\infty} \varepsilon_{\text{eff}}(\lambda) \cdot P_{BB}(T_e, \lambda) \cdot IQE(\lambda) \cdot d\lambda \quad (5)$$

where IQE is the internal quantum efficiency, q is the elementary charge, h is Planck's constant, and c the speed of light. Further information regarding the quantum efficiency measurement is displayed in Supplementary information S2.

The model described by Equations (1) to (5), when provided with the appropriate input device parameters, namely the T_c , F_{ec} , IQE , ε_e , ε_c , n , I_0 , R_{sh} , and R_S , can be used to calculate the TPV conversion efficiency as a function of the T_e .

The accurate fitting of the model to the high-temperature calorimetry experiments described above require precise knowledge of both the T_e and T_c . However, under TPV operating conditions, direct measurement of these temperatures is extremely challenging due to the presence of intense heat fluxes, which lead to significant temperature gradients and thermal non-uniformities across the system. In our setup, temperature sensors were placed as close as possible to the respective surfaces and carefully calibrated. However, despite these precautions, some measurement uncertainties remain. Based on the heat flux direction, the emitter temperature tends to be overestimated, while the cell temperature is typically underestimated.

To address this limitation, a correction procedure is applied to the experimentally measured emitter and cell temperatures. This procedure combines the model described in Equations (1) to (5) with heat conduction equations for both the emitter and the cell, given by the following two expressions:

$$T_e = T_{e,\text{exp}} - P_{\text{abs,exp}} \cdot r_e \quad (6)$$

$$T_c = T_{c,\text{exp}} + Q_{\text{dis,exp}} \cdot r_c \quad (7)$$

where r_e and r_c are the effective thermal correction factors related to the thermal resistance of the emitter and the cell, respectively. The procedure involves identifying the values of r_e and r_c that yield corrected emitter and cell temperatures resulting in the best fit between the model and the experimental I - V curves. The same values of r_e and r_c are applied across all experiments performed at different emitter temperatures, thereby ensuring that the correction method is physically consistent and independent of specific operating conditions. It is important to note that during the determination of r_e and r_c the saturation current I_0 must be also recalculated, through fitting to the I - V data, as it depends sensitively on the corrected cell temperature. The results of the model fitting for the best-performing devices presented in this work are provided in Supplementary information S6, including the values obtained for all fitting parameters.

The correction procedure described above, which re-calculates the emitter temperature through model-fitting, is intrinsically sensitive to variations in the model input parameters (IQE, ε_e , ε_c , n , I_0 , R_{sh} , R_s and F_{ec}). Among them, F_{ec} can be impacted by small variations in the relative positioning of the emitter and the cell. As explained in [23], this uncertainty is confined to approximately 1–2 %, which translates into temperature deviations of only a few degrees in the low-temperature regime and up to about 10 °C at the highest measured temperatures.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 presents the experimentally measured electric power output (P_{el}), dissipated heat (Q_{dis}), and the resulting TPV efficiency, calculated using Equation (1), as functions of the emitter temperature. These results are shown alongside the corresponding values predicted by the model described above. Data is provided for both CONV and PERC devices, allowing for direct comparison between experimental and modeled results. The detailed numerical values corresponding to these results are summarized in Table S2 and Table S3 of Supplementary information S6.

The results indicate a maximum TPV efficiency of 7.3 % for the CONV device and 6.3 % for the PERC device, with corresponding electrical power outputs of 0.92 W (1.77 W/cm²)¹ and 0.65 W (1.25 W/cm²), respectively. These values were recorded at the maximum emitter temperatures reached during testing: 1480°C for the CONV device and 1426 °C for the PERC device. As the emitter temperature decreases, the efficiency of both devices falls; however, the PERC architecture gains a relative advantage in this regime, for example, achieving 4.0 % at 1150 °C, compared to 3.8 % for the CONV device interpolating the experimental data for the same emitter temperature.

¹ In this work, the power density is defined as the P_{el} divided by the emitter area A_e , with the emitter taken to be the aperture area of the experimental setup. We use the emitter area rather than the cell area for this calculation because the cell area (1.05 cm²) is considerably larger than the portion that is actually illuminated. Under the high F_{ec} conditions of our setup, the illuminated region of the cell can be well approximated by the aperture area (0.52 cm²). Consequently, reporting power density with respect to the emitter area provides a more accurate measure of the power generated in the actively illuminated region of the cell.

Model predictions are consistent with the experimental observations and indicate that efficiency and power output could be further increased, reaching up to 8.8 % for the CONV device and 6.6 % for the PERC device, with corresponding electrical power outputs of 2.28 W (4.38 W/cm²) and 0.91 W (1.75 W/cm²), respectively, if the emitter temperature were increased to 1816 °C for the CONV device and 1537 °C for the PERC device. These values represent the performance that would be reached assuming the cell temperature remains fixed at the maximum value measured during the experiments (31.0 °C for CONV and 27.7 °C for PERC; See Supplementary information S6).

Figure 2. (A) conversion efficiency η_{TPV} , (B) electrical power P_{el} , and (C) heat dissipated Q as functions of the emitter temperature. Error bars in temperature indicate the difference between the corrected temperature (lower bound) and the experimental measurement (higher bound).

The results reveal significant differences between the CONV and PERC devices. In the high-temperature regime, these differences are mainly driven by variations in series resistance, which becomes increasingly critical at the high current densities generated under elevated irradiance. As a result, the temperature at which maximum efficiency is achieved is reduced for the PERC devices. This interpretation is consistent with the measured resistance values: the CONV device exhibits a series resistance of approximately 7.7 m Ω ·cm², while the PERC device reaches around 17.7 m Ω ·cm². Two factors account for this disparity. First, methodological: variability in the electroplating process, where increased agitation during film growth improves conductivity in the case of the CONV. Second, structural: point contacts, particularly in highly doped substrates, cannot match the performance of full-area contacts due to the low contact resistance achieved by the later, resulting in a resistance bottleneck on the rear side. A more detailed explanation of these two limiting factors is provided in Supplementary Information S7.

In the low-temperature regime the performance differences between CONV and PERC devices are mainly governed by the slightly higher OOB reflectivity of the PERC architecture, attributable to reduced absorption in the semiconductor/dielectric/metal mirror stack (see Figure S2 in Supplementary information S2). This advantage yields the marginally higher conversion efficiencies observed for PERC devices in this temperature range. Nevertheless, both architectures remain limited by substantial OOB absorption losses, dominated by FCA in the highly doped Ge substrates, which constrains efficiency improvements at lower emitter temperatures.

Figure 3 shows the modelled distribution of absorbed power within the CONV and the PERC TPV cells. These include the P_{el} , ohmic losses (I^2R_s), and heat absorption losses from both the IB ($\lambda < 1.8 \mu\text{m}$) and OOB ($\lambda > 1.8 \mu\text{m}$) spectral ranges. The results of the model confirm that in the low temperature regime, OOB absorption is the dominant loss mechanism, while at higher temperatures IB losses become increasingly significant. Ohmic losses also rise with emitter temperature but remain relatively minor, between 1

% and 2 % (absolute) of the total losses at the maximum measured efficiency point (~ 1470 °C) for the CONV and PERC cells, respectively.

Figure 3. Temperature-dependent absorbed power distributions for the CONV (A) and PERC (B) devices. The incident power is partitioned into absorbed power (IB and OOB), electrical power converted, and then the IB partition related to ohmic losses is represented for different series resistance values. Red stars indicate the experimentally measured electrical power conversion of the total power absorbed (TPV efficiency). Panels (C) and (D) show the spectral power emitted by the graphite emitter at 1480 °C, split into absorbed and reflected contributions for the CONV and PERC devices, respectively. The wavelength-dependent EQE, IQE, and absorptance are overlaid to relate the spectral absorption with the carrier collection efficiency.

4 COMPARISON WITH STATE-OF-THE-ART RESULTS

4.1 GE TPV CELLS: SEMI-EMPIRICAL PREDICTIONS

The state of the art, as previously discussed, explores several strategies to enhance the performance of Ge-based TPV devices, many of which rely on simulated spectrally selective emitters. Among these works, the only publication that provides a complete experimental dataset enabling a rigorous comparison with our model is that of Martín et al. [12], which also reports the highest efficiency obtained using a semi-empirical approach. Other studies either employ low-doped Ge substrates (e.g., Mansur et al.[21]) or lack key information necessary for accurate simulation, as in the case of Fernández et al [13]. For context, Supplementary Information S8 analyses in detail the efficiency-calculation methodologies used in the only two reported TPV devices based on highly doped Ge substrates, those of Martín et al. [12] and Fernández et al. [13].

Using a semi-empirical approach, Martín et al. [12] reported TPV efficiencies of 23.2 % at an emitter temperature of 1800 °C when pairing a Ge TPV cell (also fabricated on a highly doped substrate with a doping concentration of $10^{17} cm^{-3}$) with a theoretical spectrally selective Al/W emitter [22]. Assuming a spectrally selective emitter is the most

straightforward strategy to improve the efficiency of Ge TPV cells fabricated on thick, highly doped substrates, as this approach provides significantly larger gains than the use of BSR, whose impact is inherently limited by the strong OOB FCA of the Ge substrate.

The cells reported in [12] are theoretically capable of operating at very high emitter temperatures due to an exceptionally low series resistance of $1 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ strongly favored by a small cell area ($0.36 \times 0.36 \text{ cm}^2$) and the use of a 4-busbar front-electrode configuration. In addition, the devices exhibited higher EQE (see Figure S5 in Supplementary information S3), primarily due to a lower shadowing factor (6 %). This advantage likewise stems from the smaller cell size, which eliminates the need for a dense front metal grid to efficiently collect current.

By contrast, the devices developed in this work utilize a larger cell area (1.05 cm^2), a simpler 2-busbar front-contact layout, and a non-annealed front contact (see Supplementary information S7). These design choices result in higher series resistance (7.7 to $17.7 \text{ m}\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$) and reduced performance at elevated temperatures. The larger area also necessitates a denser front grid, leading to increased shadowing factor (19 %) and consequently lower EQE.

Figure 4. Simulations of the TPV converters presented in this work and by Martin et al. The data for efficiency (A), power density (B), and dissipated heat density (C) are shown for two scenarios: (1) devices with an active area of 0.52 cm^2 illuminated by a graphite emitter (dashed lines), and (2) devices with an active area of 0.09 cm^2 , as reported by Martin et al. [12], illuminated by a spectrally selective AlN/W emitter (solid lines). Panel (D) shows the spectral distribution of absorbed and reflected power for the CONV device under illumination from an AlN/W emitter at $1800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, together with the corresponding wavelength-dependent IQE, EQE, and absorptance. Panel (E) presents the temperature-dependent absorbed power distribution for the CONV device, separating the contributions from absorbed power (IB and OOB), electrical power converted, and ohmic losses related to the IB losses.

Figure 4 shows the predicted performance of the CONV and PERC cells developed in this work in the *Downscaled-selective-emitter* scenario where our devices are adjusted to the dimensions of the devices reported in [12] (0.09 cm^2) and illuminated by the same theoretical spectrally selective emitter described in [22] (solid lines). Conversely, it also presents the *Upscaled-graphite-emitter* scenario, where the devices from [12] are

adjusted to the dimensions of our cells and irradiated by the experimental graphite emitter used in this study (dashed lines). This rescaling includes corrections for geometrical shadowing, with the corresponding optical adjustments, as well as a correction of the series resistance to match the front-grid design of our devices. The procedure for R_s rescaling is detailed in Supplementary information S7, while the optical and shadowing adjustments follow equations provided in S2 and S3. Specifically, the values used are consistent across both studies: for the large-cell configuration (1.05 cm², 15 μm finger width, 100 μm spacing, SF = 19 %), the series resistances are 3.3 mΩ cm² (CONV), 6.2 mΩ cm² (PERC), and 4.7 mΩ cm² (Martín et al [12]). For the small-cell configuration (0.09 cm², 6 μm finger width, 94 μm spacing, SF ≈ 6 %), the corresponding R_s values are 1.4 mΩ cm² (CONV), 4.3 mΩ cm² (PERC), and 1.1 mΩ cm² (Martín et al [12]).

Remarkably, the results calculated in [12] do not consider the emitter-cell optical cavity effects, accounted for by the effective emissivity in equation (2). To enable a fair comparison, we first reproduced the results in [12] without considering emitter-cell cavity effects. We then re-evaluated the same cases with our simulation framework, which explicitly includes emitter-cell interactions, with cell temperature fixed at 25 °C, and computed the efficiencies shown in Figure 4.

Noteworthy, the simulated results in Figure 4 for both CONV and PERC devices in the *Upscaled-graphite-emitter* scenario are greater than the experimental results shown in Figure 2. This is because the simulations assume improved series resistance (annealed contacts), as discussed in Supplementary information 7.

In the *Downscaled-selective-emitter* scenario shown in Figure 4A our model predicts TPV efficiencies of 22.3 % (CONV), 21.2% (PERC), and 22.1% (Martin et al) at 1800 °C (the temperature reported in [12]). These are not the operating maxima: extending the temperature range yields peaks of 23.2 % at 2151 °C for CONV, 21.8 % at 1858 °C for PERC, and 22.7 % at 2123 °C for the device of Martin et al. Notably, the efficiency of 22.1 % predicted at 1800 °C for the Martin et al. device is lower than the value reported in their study. This discrepancy arises because our calculations account for the emitter-cell optical cavity, an effect that was neglected in their analysis.

Conversely, in the *Upscaled-graphite-emitter* scenario, the cells reported in [12] would achieve an efficiency of 8.1 % at an emitter temperature of 1480 °C the maximum temperature register in our experiments, closely matching the experimental observations obtained with our cells. Under the same graphite-emitter conditions and accounting for the potential series-resistance improvements discussed in Supplementary information 7 (i.e. annealed contacts), our devices would reach 8.1 % (CONV) and 7.9 % (PERC) at 1480 °C. As in the previous case, the temperature of maximum efficiency is higher: the achievable peaks are 11.1 % at 1983 °C for CONV, 9.3 % at 1774 °C for PERC, and 9.8 % at 1858 °C for the device of Martin et al. [12].

Two conclusions can be extracted from the comparison presented above. On the one hand, the use of spectrally selective emitters plays a crucial role in TPV device performance, especially when parasitic absorption of OOB is the dominant loss mechanism. On the other hand, the dramatical difference between experimental efficiency values and idealized semi-empirical projections based on tailored emitter spectra highlights the difficulty of standardizing efficiency calculations in TPV systems. Semi-empirical models, such as the one presented in [12], often rely on idealizations that fail to reflect the performance of real devices. Furthermore, their accuracy depends on precise knowledge of all relevant optical, thermal and electrical properties of constituent

materials, as well as their mutual interaction. This requirement is at odds with the intrinsic complexity and variety of TPV systems, including factors such as emitter spectral characteristics, view factor, optical cavity design, and device geometry. The results reported in this work therefore emphasize the importance of direct experimental calorimetry measurements which, when rigorously implemented, provide a reliable basis for assessing TPV performance under realistic operating conditions.

4.2 INGAAS TPV CELLS: DIRECT CALORIMETRY MEASUREMENTS

Experimental efficiency measurements of TPV devices based on InGaAs PV absorbers have been widely reported in the recent literature, providing a useful reference point for placing the performance of Ge-based converters into context. Among these studies, only a subset employs direct calorimetry, i.e., measurements in which both Q_{dis} and P_{el} are experimentally determined, allowing a true in-situ determination of TPV efficiency. To establish a consistent basis for discussion, Table 2 compiles the key experimental parameters reported in studies that quantify TPV efficiency using calorimetric techniques. To better visualize the performance trends across these studies, the compiled data are also represented in Figure 5.

Among these studies, our previous work (López et al. [23]) was carried out using the same calorimetric setup as in the present study. This unique overlap enables the first fully consistent comparison between InGaAs and Ge TPV devices under identical experimental conditions, as discussed later in this section.

Table 2 Summary of experimental reports on TPV efficiencies obtained through calorimetry methods.

Work	Material	Cell Area/ Aperture Area ⁱ [cm ²]	Emitter material	Emitter- to-Cell view factor F_{ec}	P_{el} [W] @ $T_{\text{emitter, max}}$ (Power density [W/cm ²])	Max TPV efficiency reported
Wernsman et al [31]	InGaAs	4.0/4.0	SiC ion- etched	-	3.16 (0.79) ^{iv}	23.6 @ 1039 °C
Siergiej et al [32]	InGaAs/InPAs	4.0/4.0	SiC ion- etched	-	3.60 (0.9) ⁱⁱ	16.5 @ 1058 °C
Lopez et al [23]	InGaAs	1.05/0.52	Graphite	0.95	2.51 (4.85) ^v	26.4 % @ 1592 °C
Mahorter et al [33]	InGaAs/InPAs	4.0/4.0	SiC ion- etched	-	-	20.6 % @ 1060 °C
Narayan et al [34]	GaAs InGaAs	0.91/0.91 0.62/0.62	Graphite	-	2.23 (2.45) ⁱⁱ 0.41 (0.66) ⁱⁱ	31 % @ 2330 °C 30 % @ 1300 °C
Tervo et al [35]	GaInAs GaInPAs/ GaInAs	0.8/0.64	Graphite	0.31	2.42-3.02 (3.78) ⁱⁱⁱ 3.70-4.62 (5.78) ⁱⁱⁱ	38.8% @ 1850 °C 36.8 % @ 1900 °C
LaPotin et al [8]	InGaAs multijunction 1.4/1.2 1.2/1.0	0.81/ 0.72	Wolfram halogen bulb	0.107	1.72-1.94 (2.39) ⁱⁱⁱ 1.30-1.46 (1.80) ⁱⁱⁱ	41.1% @ 2400 °C 38.9 % @ 2178 °C
CONV	Ge	1.05/0.52	Graphite	0.95	0.92 (1.77) ^{iv}	7.3 % @ 1485 °C
PERC	Ge	1.05/0.52	Graphite	0.95	0.65 (1.22) ^{iv}	6.3 % @ 1432 °C

ⁱ The cell area corresponds to the total mesa-defined cell area (i.e., the area enclosed by the mesa etch), while the aperture area defines the opening through which radiation is transmitted. Owing to beam

divergence downstream of the aperture, the illuminated region on the cell may extend beyond the aperture footprint.

ii The study reports power density only. Total power was calculated by multiplying the reported power density by the aperture (cell) area, which are identical in this work.

iii The study reports power density only and does not specify the reference area. The power range shown was obtained by multiplying the reported power density by the aperture area (lower bound) and the cell area (upper bound).

iv The study reports both power and power density, with power density defined as total power divided by the aperture area.

v The study reports both absolute power and power density. Power density is defined as the total electrical power normalized between two possible areas: the graphite emitter area (0.5 cm^2) or to the TPV cell active area (0.7 cm^2). For consistency throughout this work, all power-density calculations are normalized to the aperture area of 0.52 cm^2 , as detailed in the footnote on page 8 [23].

Figure 5A shows electrical power as a function of dissipated heat, while Figure 5B shows the electrical power density as a function of total dissipated heat density, including results from [8], [23], [31], [32], [33], [34], [35]. Each point in these graphs corresponds to a unique heat-power combination, with the corresponding TPV efficiency indicated by the green color scale in the background. The marker color, following a red-scale colormap, corresponds to the emitter temperature at which the device was tested. Figure 5C and D show the electrical power density and conversion efficiency as a function of the emitter temperature for the same experimental results shown in Figure 5A and B.

The figure highlights the markedly higher efficiency of InGaAs-based devices, founded on their thin-film architecture due to the very high absorption coefficients inherent in direct-bandgap semiconductors. This design supports higher V_{oc} , lower R_s , and superior OOB photon reflection. By contrast, Ge-based TPV devices suffer from substantial OOB absorption due to their thick substrates, which also limit the achievable V_{oc} . As a result, Ge-based devices exhibit not only lower efficiency but also reduced power density, driven mainly by the lower V_{oc} and short-circuit current.

It is important to note that the reduced power density of Ge-based devices is not directly evident in Figure 5C, since the experimental studies compared there employed different view factors and thermal emitters. These variations explain the discrepancies in absolute power and power density across the datasets.

Figure 5. Measured (A) heat and power and (B) heat and power densities, for state of the art InGaAs TPV devices, measured using calorimetric techniques, as reported in Table 2. Each data point in graphs (A) and (B) corresponds to a unique heat-power combination, with the corresponding TPV efficiency indicated by the green color scale. The marker color, following a red-scale colormap, corresponds to the emitter temperature at which the device was tested. (C) shows the power density as a function of emitter temperature, based on calorimetric measurements normalized by the illuminated area. (D) displays TPV efficiencies obtained through calorimetric methods as a function of emitter temperature. Some data points are absent from specific panels due to missing information required for plotting, such as incomplete calorimetric power reporting (e.g., Mahorter et al. [33]). For Tervo et al. [35] and Lapotin et al. [8], the absolute electrical power in panel (A) was calculated assuming an average between the aperture area and the total cell area, because the original works do not clearly state which area was used to compute the reported power.

Given the methodological equivalence highlighted above, Figure 6 presents experimental results for InGaAs devices reported in our earlier work [23] alongside those of the CONV cell examined here. All results are referenced to the emitter temperature directly measured in our setup, without applying the thermal emitter temperature correction described above. Such a correction cannot be applied to the results in [23], as the necessary optical characterization data are not available.

As shown in Figure 6, under identical experimental conditions (i.e. an uncorrected emitter temperature of approximately 1590°C), InGaAs devices achieved an efficiency of 26.4 % and an output power of 2.51 W ($V_{mpp} = 416$ mV, $I_{mpp} = 6.04$ A), whereas Ge TPV cells reached only 7.1 % efficiency with an output power of 0.86 W ($V_{mpp} = 285$ mV, $I_{mpp} =$

3.0 A). These results demonstrate that InGaAs TPV cells deliver nearly three times the output power and approximately 3.5 times the conversion efficiency of Ge cells under the same conditions. This direct comparison highlights the clear performance advantage of InGaAs. Noteworthy, this advantage would likely be even greater if record-performing InGaAs devices with enhanced OOB photon recycling and improved carrier collection were considered [8], [30], [35].

Figure 6. Cost and performance comparison of Ge and InGaAs devices as a function of the uncorrected emitter temperature (°C). Panels show (A) I_{mpp} [A], (B) V_{mpp} [mV], (C) P_{mpp} [W], and (D) η [%]. Panels (E) and (F) present the cost of power (in €/W) as a function of emitter temperature (in °C) and the cost per unit of cell area (in €/cm²) for both Ge and InGaAs devices, respectively. The cost of power (€/W) is computed as the ratio of the cost per area (in €/cm²) and the measured electrical power density (in W/cm²). The color scale highlights regions with low cost of power (blue, < 10 €/W) and high cost of power (red, > 10 €/W). The dashed horizontal lines indicate representative device costs used for comparison (10 €/cm² for Ge and 70 €/cm² for InGaAs [4]), allowing direct reading of the resulting €/W versus emitter temperature at those assumed cost levels.

Nonetheless, while InGaAs-based devices clearly outperform Ge in both efficiency and power density, Ge retains a competitive niche in applications where the cost of power (€/W) is the dominant techno-economic metric, such as industrial waste-heat recovery. In these scenarios, the low operating cost of TPV cells—driven by the low cost of the incident photons [4]—means that the levelized cost of electricity is largely determined by the capital expenditure of the TPV converter itself (in €/W), rather than by its efficiency [3], [4].

The lower material and fabrication cost of Ge can therefore compensate for its reduced electrical performance. For example, at an emitter temperature of 1455 °C, a Ge TPV cell with a device cost of 10 €/cm² [4] and a power density of 1.09 W/cm² results in a cost of power of 9.2 €/W. Under the same conditions, an InGaAs device costing 70 €/cm² [4] and delivering 3.41 W/cm² yields 20.5 €/W, corresponding to a cost ratio of approximately 2.2 in favor of Ge. Similar trends are obtained when the analysis is extended across the investigated emitter temperature range, with the Ge-to-InGaAs cost-of-power ratio varying between approximately 2.2 and 2.5 for the cost assumptions considered. Further insights are provided in Figure 6, panels E and F, which illustrates the cost of power as a function of both emitter temperature and device cost for both Ge (panel E) and InGaAs (panel F) devices.

By contrast, the use of higher efficiency InGaAs devices becomes critical in applications with substantial operational expenditures, that is, where the incident photons carry a high associated cost, such as thermal batteries or fuel-driven TPV systems. In these cases, increased TPV efficiency directly reduces the thermal input required per unit of electrical output, thereby lowering operating costs. Under such conditions, the superior efficiency of InGaAs-based TPV cells can justify their higher capital cost, particularly at sufficiently high emitter temperatures where high power densities can be sustained [4].

The use of lower-efficiency but low-cost Ge devices can also be justified in applications with significant operational costs (e.g., thermal batteries or fuel-driven TPV systems) when the heat dissipated in the cell is recovered for heating purposes. In such cases, leveraging this waste heat can increase the overall system efficiency, enabling economically attractive combined heat and power solutions for buildings and low-temperature industrial applications [36].

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this work we have provided, to our knowledge, the first fully empirical determination of Ge-based TPV efficiencies under high-temperature, high-irradiance operation. Two device architectures on highly doped p-type Ge ($\approx 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) were fabricated and tested under these conditions, using a graphite emitter and a high view-factor (≈ 0.95) calorimetric setup. The conventional design with a full-area Au rear contact achieved 7.3 % efficiency and 1.77 W cm^{-2} at $1480 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, while the PERC-type device reached 6.3 % and 1.22 W cm^{-2} at $1426 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The higher peak efficiency of the conventional cell is attributed to its lower series resistance under the large current densities induced at elevated temperatures. Conversely, at lower emitter temperatures the PERC architecture exhibits a modest advantage (e.g., 4.0 % vs. 3.8 % at $1150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) due to improved rear-side reflectivity that curtails sub-bandgap absorption.

A theoretical model, validated against both architectures across temperature, reproduces the measurements and clarifies the internal loss budget. The analysis identifies OOB photon losses, dominated by FCA in the highly doped Ge substrate, as the primary efficiency limiter under the experimental (graphite emitter) conditions. Using the validated model, we reconciled prior literature by re-evaluating state-of-the-art devices under two scenarios. On the one hand, devices in the literature [12] modeled under our graphite spectrum, results in efficiencies $\sim 8.1 \text{ }%$ near $1450\text{--}1500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, consistent with the efficiencies experimentally measured for our devices. On the other hand, under idealized, spectrally selective AlN/W emission, our own conventional device could approach efficiencies of approximately 22 % at temperatures around $2000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, in line with earlier semi-empirical projections.

Finally, this work also provided the first direct comparison between Ge- and InGaAs-based TPV devices measured under an identical experimental conditions, including the same emitter, view factor, and calorimetric protocol, thereby avoiding ambiguities associated with purely electrical or optically inferred metrics. Under these conditions, InGaAs devices achieve approximately three times higher output power and conversion efficiency than Ge cells. This difference is associated with the thin-film architecture of InGaAs, which enables higher operating voltages, reduced series resistance, and more effective OOB photon recycling. In contrast, thick, highly doped Ge substrates exhibit stronger free-carrier absorption and enhanced non-radiative recombination, resulting in lower operating voltages as well as reduced efficiency and power density.

Despite its lower performance, the lower cost of Ge TPV cells represents a clear advantage in applications with low operational costs, such as industrial waste-heat recovery, where the capital expenditure becomes the dominant cost component. Under these conditions, Ge TPV cells must be approximately two to three times less expensive than InGaAs cells to achieve a lower cost per unit power capacity—a condition that is currently met in practice. Conversely, in applications where the thermal input carries a significant cost, such as thermal batteries or fuel-driven TPV systems, operational expenditures become increasingly important, and higher TPV efficiency plays a more significant role in reducing overall levelized cost of generated electricity.

Future work should focus on improving the performance of germanium-based TPV devices through effective spectral control strategies, such as spectrally selective emitters or optical filters, to better match the incident spectrum to the Ge bandgap. In addition, substrate optimization—particularly through the use of lower-doped and/or thinner substrates—can reduce free-carrier absorption and non-radiative recombination losses. Together, these approaches offer a clear pathway to enhancing efficiency and power density, further improving the viability of Ge TPV cells in a broader range of applications.

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